

THE IMPORTANCE OF SMALL BUSINESS AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN THE ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: The article details small business and entrepreneurship, its role in the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, its development in our country and foreign experience in this field, information about the benefits provided to small businesses.

Keywords: small business, private entrepreneurship, economy, government, taxes, income, GDP

Small business and entrepreneurship are important factors in the development of the economy, increasing employment and income of the population. More than fifty decrees and resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan have been adopted over the past two and a half years in order to fully support representatives of this sphere. In particular, the procedures for state registration of entrepreneurial activity, obtaining various permits and many other services have been simplified. For the convenience of this, the Public Services Agency and its centers on the ground were created. The position of the Commissioner for the Protection of the rights and legitimate interests of business entities (business Ombudsman) has been introduced. Reception offices of the Prime Minister have been created in all regions, which accept and help solve the appeals of entrepreneurs. Under the Cabinet of Ministers, a State fund created to support the development of entrepreneurship, for which 200 billion soums and 50 \$ million were allocated. The volume of loans provided to entrepreneurs by commercial banks has increased. Such practical measures pay off. Small business and entrepreneurship provide about 60% of the gross domestic product of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a third of the volume of industrial products, 98% of agricultural products, half of investments. In many regions, 70-90% of exports are accounted for by small businesses. For 6 months of this year, the number of business entities increased by 60 thousand [1].

Small business and entrepreneurship are the sphere of labor use and a source of income for a significant part of the population. Often, only socially unprotected segments of the population can find a job in it: women, young people looking for work for the first time, who do not have secondary education and work experience. Small business has become one of the most important

factors in the economic development of our country. Changes in the economy of Uzbekistan contribute to the creation of additional jobs and an increase in incomes of the population, creating the necessary competitive environment for this sphere. Due to the fact that our people have been engaged in small business for centuries, there are ample opportunities for the development of small business and entrepreneurship in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Small business and private entrepreneurship are of particular importance in the process of sustainable economic development, as they ensure the creation of new jobs, contributing additional revenues to the budget. Nowadays it is impossible to imagine the entire world economy without small businesses. Small business and private entrepreneurship play an important role in the development of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The development of small business and private entrepreneurship is connected with the peculiarities of the local region itself. Social, demographic and availability of resources in the region affect the definition of regional characteristics of the business.

The development of small business and private entrepreneurship in the Republic of Uzbekistan over the years of independence and up to the present day has passed certain stages. In this regard, a number of regulations and legal bases have been created.

Stages of development of small business and private entrepreneurship [2]

Stage	Years	Relevant regulatory documents
I	1992-1995	“Regulations on Small enterprises in the Republic of Uzbekistan” (Appendix 2 to the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of February 26, 1992 No. 85)
II	1995-1998	The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On stimulating the development of small business and private entrepreneurship" (December 21, 1995)
III	1998-2003	Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures and measures to further stimulate the development of private entrepreneurship, small and medium-sized businesses" (April 9, 1998)
IV	2003-2011	Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On approval of the classification of enterprises and organizations related to small Business Entities”(October 11, 2003)
	2011-	Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of

V	2019	Uzbekistan “ On amendments to the classification of enterprises and organizations related to small business entities (business)”dated June 14, 2013, resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “ On additional measures to further improve the investment climate and business climate in the Republic of Uzbekistan” dated April 7, 2014, July 3, 2014), Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the Strategy of Actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan”(Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947 dated February 7, 2017)
VI	2020- 2022 later period s	Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 9, 2020 No. PF-5969 ”on priority measures to mitigate the negative impact of the coronavirus pandemic and the global crisis on economic sectors“, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures to support the population, economic sectors and business entities during the coronavirus pandemic" - Decree No. PF-5978 dated April 3, 2020). Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 30, 2022 No. PP-364 “On measures to implement the tasks set within the framework of the ”open dialogue” with entrepreneurs in 2022“ (Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 30, 2022 No. PP-364) Resolution PF-29 "On priority areas of state policy to reduce

The goal of the 29th new development strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 is to create conditions for the organization of entrepreneurial activity and the formation of a permanent source of income, bringing the share of entrepreneurship in GDP to 80 percent and the share of exports to 60 percent. Issues such as the opening of 200 new industrial zones in the regions and the development of a system of business incubators, support for entrepreneurship in the regions, reduction of unemployment and poverty are highlighted separately.

In all countries of the world, small business and private entrepreneurship are the basis of the national economy. One of the economic values of small business development is to ensure a quantitative increase in the country's GDP. As a result of state support for small business and private entrepreneurship, the share of small business and private entrepreneurship in the country's GDP in 2021 amounted to 54.9 percent.

The share of small business and private entrepreneurship in the national economy [2]

Indications	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
GDP	65,3	62,4	56,0	55,7	54,9	51,8
Industry	41,2	37,4	25,8	27,9	27,0	25,9
Construction	64,8	73,2	75,8	72,5	72,4	71,6
Busyness	78,0	76,3	76,2	74,5	74,4	74,4
Export	22,0	27,2	27,0	20,5	22,3	29,5
Import	53,6	56,2	61,6	51,7	48,7	49,4

Indeed, small business and private entrepreneurship are becoming an industry that fills the domestic market with local goods and services, supplies parts and spare parts for large enterprises and increases the export potential of the country. This can also be seen by increasing the country's position in the export potential. The role of small business in foreign economic activity is gradually increasing. Small business is also becoming the most important sector of the country's economy.

The volume of the main indicators of small business and private entrepreneurship in the sectors of the economy [2]

Indications	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Industry (billion sum)	61367,8	87962,0	83344,2	103020,8	121719,2	142611,7
Construction (billion sum)	22469,4	37451,7	53960,9	63866,6	77762,0	93620,8
Busyness (one thousand people)	10541,5	10128,8	19318,9	9865,7	10070,7	10222,9
Exports (millions of US Dollars)	2759,3	3810,8	4714,8	3100,9	3711,2	5696,2

Imports (millions of US Dollars)	7511,9	10916,2	14972,2	10943,3	12389,0	15154,1
Trade (billion sum)	92973,0	114896, 4	138920, 7	164106, 1	204787, 4	253573, 4
Agriculture, forestry and fisheries (billion sum)	152010, 5	191759, 2	219466, 9	253238, 2	307280, 2	347222, 0
Services (billion sum)	69212,7	84433,4	103106, 6	114052, 7	144812, 7	173157, 7
Delivery (million tons)	548,8	611,7	641,0	638,9	678,9	588,1
Cargo turnover (million tons km)	10444,4	11657,7	12152,3	12304,6	13108,1	14394,9
Passenger transportatio n (million passengers)	5037,5	5242,6	5345,0	4904,8	5237,6	5606,0
Passenger turnover (million km)	111435, 0	115335, 2	117412, 7	107766, 7	114681, 5	123882, 5

The weight of small businesses in agriculture, trade, consumer services, catering, hotel and tourism activities is very large. In the subsequent time, industries are also developing in rural areas as a result of modernization, technical and technological transformation of production, structural transformations and diversification of industry. The role of small business in industrial production is also growing from year to year.

We see that over the past two decades, according to some indicators, it has increased 5-10 times, and according to others - 200-300 times. Especially great positive changes have taken place in industry, construction, trade, agriculture, forestry and fisheries.

It can be said that small business in our country has been developing for a long time for the reason that potters, jewelers, confectioners, weavers and

other craftsmen have been engaged in the manufacture of household items, tools, jewelry, products for centuries. Those who made embroidery, clothes, shoes and other products individually or with their family members in their small workshops. The bulk of these goods were sent for sale along the Great Silk Road. The development of small business was also promoted by favorable natural and climatic conditions, hard work of the people, rich raw materials. In modern Uzbekistan, small business is represented by individual entrepreneurs, micro firms, small enterprises, as well as peasant and farm farms. In order to ensure the most favorable business environment, various benefits and preferences are provided to business entities, and comprehensive support is provided. Privatization is the basis for the formation of a mixed economy and the further development of market relations. During the years of independence, about 86.7 thousand state-owned enterprises and facilities were privatized. As a result, a new social stratum of society has emerged for Uzbekistan – the class of owners, numbering about 6.5 million people. Along with privatization, small business also developed rapidly, which in turn served as the basis for the formation of a market economy and a competitive environment in Uzbekistan.

Foreign experience shows that in developed countries, small enterprises account for 80-97% of the total number of enterprises, employ more than half of the able-bodied population, and produce up to 70% of the national product. In Singapore, for example, about 80 percent of the total employed population is employed in small businesses. This provides 4-5% of GDP. In China, small enterprises produce most of the products and services. The main share of goods exported to China is accounted for by small businesses [3].

Small business has become one of the most important factors in the economic development of Uzbekistan. At the end of 2015, its share in GDP was 52.5%, and in 2010 -31%. The share of people employed in this sector in the total employed population increased from 49.7% in 2010 to 74.6% in 2015. The conducted research has shown that during the years of independence, a solid legislative framework has been created in Uzbekistan, which determines the priority of private property – the basis of a market economy. A favorable business climate and reliable legal guarantees for the accelerated development of small business and entrepreneurship have emerged as the most important factor in the formation of a middle class of owners, the sustainable development of our country's economy, the creation of new jobs and new jobs. The rapid development of small business is associated with the liberalization of the economy and the creation of a qualitatively new business environment. This

led to a reduction in the level of costs in economic management and an increase in the efficiency of the use of material, labor and financial resources and allowed more to be spent on the development of production. Since the first years of the establishment of the foundations of a market economy, the leadership of Uzbekistan has paid great attention to the development of the legislative framework and the organization of financial support.

An urgent solution is needed to create a stable tax system. While an entrepreneur does not have clear legislative guarantees that new taxes will not appear tomorrow, he hides his income, thereby reducing the level of tax collection. But they only affect debt at the same time as restructuring and tax amnesty. Although this involves a lot of costs, the measure is necessary. In addition, we must understand that a reasonable and fair tax reform will initially lead to a decrease, not an increase, in the total revenue of the Treasury. The absence of systematic, reliable and complete information comprehensively characterizing the state of the market, nothing hinders the company's activities. Today, manufacturers and sellers of goods are forced to use fragmentary information from advertising materials. Therefore, the organization of national and territorial information and commercial networks and centers, information banks, their educational and methodological [4].

Information centers collect information about enterprises and organizations, price dynamics, including world prices for individual goods, insurance rates, exchange rates, dates of exhibitions, fairs and auctions. This is part of the measures aimed at supporting small businesses that can really increase their level of development. Entrepreneurs positively perceive the idea of strengthening state regulation of economic processes in our country. We cannot allow all innovations to be reduced to another wave of regulation. In the following years, significant work was carried out to create conditions and a favorable environment for the development of private entrepreneurship, doing business, and widely attracting domestic and foreign investments in the economy. Special attention is paid to the field of democratization and liberalization of the economy, the creation of effective mechanisms to support small businesses and entrepreneurship. The list of licensing procedures in accordance with the laws "on licensing procedures in the field of entrepreneurial activity", "on competition", "on guarantees of freedom of entrepreneurial activity" (in the new edition) and other legislative acts, the types of which the requirements necessary for entrepreneurial activity are consistently reduced, in recent years only 160% of licensing procedures passed the licensing procedure.

More than 44 percent, 19 or 25 percent say the cancellation reduces the number of activities subject to licensing. The forms and frequency of submission of statistical, tax and financial statements to state bodies by business entities have been reduced by 1.5-2 times. It should be noted that the expenses of business entities for the passage of licensing procedures were reduced by about 8 times, the fee for opening bank accounts was canceled and other measures were taken. [5].

References:

1. <https://uza.uz/oz/posts/kichik-biznes-va-tadbirkorlikni-rivojlantirish-bo-yicha-yang-23-07-2019>.
2. Author development
3. Балашевич М. И. «Малый бизнес: отечественный и зарубежный опыт». Учебное пособие. Минск-2001
4. Примова А. А. «Тексты лекций по курсу «Малый бизнес и предпринимательство» Бухара -2013г.
5. O. T. Sattorqulov, B. B. Toshboev. O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotida Kichik biznes va tadbirkorlikning o'rni va ahamiyati. // Yosh olim. - 2015. - No 6 (86). - S. 455-458.
6. Nishonboyev Doniyor Erkinjon o'g'li. (2023). The Character of the Development of International Economic Relations. Information Horizons: American Journal of Library and Information Science Innovation (2993-2777), 1(8), 29-33.
7. Yuldashev Doniyor, & Nishonboyev Doniyor. (2022). Competitiveness of a family business ways to improve. international journal of social science & interdisciplinary research ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact Factor: 7.429, 11(10), 175-183.
8. Doniyor, Y. ., & Doniyor, N. . (2022). Content and Main Components of the Economic Mechanism of Family Business Development. Miasto Przyszłości, 28, 411-418.
9. Одина Насридиновна, Т., & Дониер Эркинжон угли, Н. (2022). Ўзбекистонда давлат бюджетини режалаштириш тизимини такомиллаштириш. Results of National Scientific Research International Journal, 1(3), 75-82.
10. Тешабаева Одина Насридиновна, & Нишонбоев Дониер Эркинжон Угли (2022). Направления совершенствования бюджетной политики в новом узбекистане. Talqin va tadqiqotlar ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali, 4 (4), 56-60.

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12. Shahbozho'ja K. ., & Elmurod, U. . (2023). Approaches to Ensuring the Welfare of the Population and Assessing Poverty. *European journal of business startups and open society*, 3(2), 84–88.
13. Karimov, S. H. (2021). Improvement of the personnel management system in the hotel business when organizing tourist routes. *Cognitio rerum*, (7), 20-22.

